

Polarization independent silicon grating antenna based on subwavelength metamaterials

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Abstract

Optical antennas are key components of an optical phased array system, enabling light coupling between the chip and the free space. In such systems, surface gratings are commonly used as antenna elements, which however suffer from a strong polarization sensitivity of their scattering angle and efficiency. Here, we experimentally demonstrate a surface grating antenna with polarization insensitive behavior on the 500 nm silicon-on-insulator platform exploiting subwavelength metamaterials. The antenna successfully achieves the same diffraction angle of 10° for both TE and TM polarizations, an estimated scattering efficiency of -4 dB, and a difference in diffraction efficiency between the two polarizations smaller than 1 dB over a bandwidth of 31 nm. This antenna facilitates efficient light coupling into and out of photonic integrated circuits.

1 Introduction

Optical Phased Arrays (OPAs) for on-chip beam forming and steering represent a promising alternative to traditional mechanically moving components in various applications, notably in light detection and ranging (LiDAR) and free-space optical communications [1–5]. Integrated optical antennas, which are responsible of emitting and receiving light into and from the free space, are the fundamental components of an OPA. Although recent literature demonstrated optical antennas based on metallic structures, dielectric pillars, fiber lenses, photonic crystals and ceramics [6–9], dielectric surface gratings are still the most popular

choice for OPAs because of their relative ease of fabrication and the possibility of achieving high efficiency [10–14]. Surface gratings with high diffraction performances for either transverse-electric (TE) or transverse-magnetic (TM) waveguide modes have been extensively reported in the literature [15–26], especially exploiting L-shaped diffraction elements to break the vertical symmetry and achieve high directionality [18, 27–30]. Grating antennas with specially designed features such as an optimized radiation pattern, improved steerability, and reduced grating lobes have been reported as well [31–34]. Nonetheless, the main drawback of surface gratings is their strong polarization sensitivity, which cause TE and TM modes to be diffracted at different angles and with different efficiencies [35]. The dependence of the optical behavior of the antenna on the polarization of the light often represents a significant challenge, for example in implementing polarization division multiplexing in optical communication systems or ensuring consistent and reliable coupling efficiencies of receiver devices. Polarization sensitivity is particularly pronounced in the high contrast, silicon-on-insulator (SOI) platform commonly used for the development of OPAs because of its strong waveguide birefringence. Nonetheless, optical antennas with a single feeding waveguide capable of effectively supporting both TE and TM polarizations would be extremely beneficial for enhancing the robustness and performance of OPA systems. To overcome this limitation without moving to a different platform or introducing additional materials, subwavelength grating metamaterials (SWG) has been explored in the literature as a promising path [36–39]. SWGs are realized by arranging their unit cells at a distance much smaller than the wavelength, resulting in an effective artificial material whose optical properties can be controlled by modifying the geometry of the unit cells [40]. For example, by exploiting the additional degree of freedom offered by SWG metamaterials, a fiber grating coupler with a difference between TE and TM coupling efficiencies smaller than 1 dB over a bandwidth of 12 nm was experimentally demonstrated in [36] on an air-cladded, suspended membrane waveguide.

In this work, we report on the design and experimental demonstration of an efficient and polarization insensitive grating antenna for free-space coupling based on SWG metamaterials and an L-shaped geometry. The antenna is realized on a 500-nm SOI platform, does not require the removal of the buried oxide, has an oxide top cladding, and a compact footprint of $6.4 \mu\text{m} \times 2.9 \mu\text{m}$. 3D FDTD simulations show that both TE and TM polarized modes are diffracted with the same scattering angle of 10° with an upward diffraction efficiency of -2.8 dB and -2.4 dB, respectively. The experimental characterization of the antenna, performed with a fiber-based setup, is in good agreement with simulations and demonstrates a difference in TE-TM coupling efficiency at 10° smaller than 1 dB over a 31 nm wavelength range, with an estimated free-space upward scattering efficiency of -4 dB.

2 Design of the surface grating antenna

2.1 Grating optimization

In order to design the antenna, we start by the diffraction angle of the grating, which can be calculated through the grating equation [38]:

$$\sin(\theta) = \frac{n_B}{n_C} + m \frac{\lambda}{n_C \Lambda_x} \quad (1)$$

where n_B is the effective index of the Bloch mode of the grating, n_C is the refractive index of the cladding material, Λ_x is the period of the grating (in the propagation direction x , as defined in Figure 1 (a)) and λ is the wavelength, 1550 nm for the design considered here. In order for the TE and TM modes to be diffracted with the same angle, resulting in a polarization insensitive grating, it is required that n_B be the same for the two polarizations, a condition that cannot be generally fulfilled in common SOI gratings. We achieve this objective by incorporating SWG metamaterials into the grating unit cell to engineer the birefringence of the grating waveguide [41]. The grating structure, as schematically represented in Figure 1 (a), includes two sections. The first one is an SWG metamaterial of length of L_{SWG} , with a transverse period in the y direction of Λ_y and duty cycle ff_y . By adjusting the value of ff_y , it is possible to control the equivalent effective refractive index and the birefringence of the metamaterial, as represented in the cross-sectional view of Figure 1 (b). The second section is an L-shaped geometry, partially etched to 50% of the waveguide height for a length of L_s and with an un-etched part of length L_u . The use of an L-shaped geometry is the key to achieve strong directionality and high upward diffraction efficiency [27]. The grating has a total period $\Lambda_x = L_{\text{SWG}} + L_s + L_u$ in the propagation direction x . The effective refractive index of the grating Bloch mode can be approximately computed as

$$n_B = (n_{\text{SWG}} \frac{L_{\text{SWG}}}{\Lambda_x}) + (n_s \frac{L_s}{\Lambda_x}) + (n_u \frac{L_u}{\Lambda_x}), \quad (2)$$

where n_{SWG} , n_s and n_u are the effective indices of the fundamental 1-D modes that are supported in the corresponding sections of the unit cell for the polarization of interest, as shown in Figure 1(b). The effective refractive index n_{SWG} of the SWG section can be changed by changing its duty cycle ff_y . To optimize the performance of the antenna, we define two convenient parameters:

$$R_L = \frac{L_s}{L_s + L_u}$$
$$ff_x = \frac{L_s + L_u}{\Lambda_x},$$

Figure 1: Schematic of the grating antenna. (a) Perspective view and (b) cross section.

being R_L the duty cycle of the L-shaped geometry only and ff_x the duty cycle of the entire unit cell of the grating. We then exploit Equation (2) to estimate the Bloch effective indices of both TE and TM modes. For each value of R_L , we computed the grating duty cycle ff_x which is needed to obtain $n_B^{\text{TE}} = n_B^{\text{TM}}$ as a function of the SWG duty cycle ff_y . With this approach, we obtained the curves shown in Figure 2 which represent a set of polarization insensitive designs for the grating. The results are reported for a silicon thickness of both 300 nm and 500 nm. The curves for a silicon thickness of 220 nm are not shown since not only the curves for different values are very close to each other, but all the points on the curves have ff_x smaller than 0.1. This means that for a typical grating pitch in the range of a couple hundred nanometers, the smallest feature size of the L-shaped region is below 100 nm, which complicates fabrication. We then compute the upward diffraction efficiency P_{upward} for both polarizations for the different design possibilities reported in Figure 2 using 3D FDTD simulations. The grating periods Λ_x of 800 nm and 680 nm were chosen for the 300 nm and 500 nm silicon thickness, respectively, to avoid second order diffraction. Simulation results as a function of R_L and ff_y are shown in Figure 3. P_{upward} for the TE polarized mode shows comparable results between two platforms while the 500 nm silicon thickness has noticeable better performance over the 300 nm silicon for TM polarization. This is caused by the lower confinement of TM polarized light for thinner waveguides which results in less interaction with waveguide perturbations. It was also shown in [22] that it is difficult for thin grating structure to radiate large amount of TM polarized light. The fact that the performance of the grating for TE polarized light hardly further improves aligns with the observation made in [16]. As a result, 500 nm silicon is chosen as the platform for further optimizations. In particular, we sweep the three parameters R_L , ff_y and Λ_x in order to obtain the highest P_{upward} for both polarizations simultaneously, considering a fixed buried oxide thickness $t_{\text{BOX}} =$

Figure 2: Combinations of ff_x and ff_y duty cycles corresponding to polarization-insensitive antenna designs with different R_L for 300 nm and 500 nm silicon thicknesses.

$3 \mu m$, the thickness of the upper cladding $t_{TOX} = 2.2 \mu m$ and the period of the SWG metamaterial $\Lambda_Y = 300$ nm. The parameter sweep allows to determine the values as $R_L=0.45$, $ff_y=0.6$ and $\Lambda_x=643$ nm. In addition to P_{upward} , one of the most important figures of merits of an antenna is its footprint, which puts constraints on its array integration and directly determines the beamwidth of the far-field (Fraunhofer) pattern through the antenna effective aperture size [42]. The optimization of the antenna's overall length and width involves adjusting the number of diffraction periods in both the x and y directions (N_x, N_y) to investigate their impact on the far-field beamwidth and the upward diffraction efficiency (P_{upward}). Figure 4 shows the results of the 3D FDTD simulations. As expected, increasing the number of periods in the propagation direction N_x improves the diffraction efficiency up to the point where no undiffracted light remains in the grating. Likewise, a larger antenna (larger number of transversal SWG periods N_y) improves P_{upward} by providing a better mode confinement until the effect of the grating lateral sidewalls becomes negligible. Conversely, a larger antenna cause a reduction of the beamwidth in the far field for both azimuth ϕ and elevation θ direction. We chose $N_x=10$ and $N_y=9$ as the

Figure 3: Scattering efficiency P_{upward} for points along the polarization-insensitive curves of Figure 2. (a) 300 nm silicon, TE mode, (b) 300 nm silicon, TM mode, (c) 500 nm silicon, TE mode, and (d) 500 nm silicon, TM mode.

optimal number of periods ensuring a compact antenna footprint of $6.4 \mu\text{m} \times 2.9 \mu\text{m}$ with a limited penalty on its efficiency.

2.2 Optimization of the injection waveguide

A rib waveguide with an etched depth of 250 nm is used as the input waveguide for the grating because this solution has been proven to effectively reduce back reflection at the grating interface [15]. However, the optimized grating antenna proposed here has an overall width of $2.9 \mu\text{m}$ and it is not practical to have a $2.9 \mu\text{m}$ -wide input waveguide while maintaining single mode operation since higher order transverse mode can easily be excited in practice. Therefore, we designed a rib-waveguide-based inverse taper as the input stage of the antenna to connect it with rest of the components on the circuit, as shown in Figure 1(a). Initially, the guided modes are confined in the rib region. As the rib becomes thinner, modes are pushed downward into the slab and then injected into the antenna. The initial width of the inverse taper w_1 needs to be properly designed such that only the fundamental TE and TM mode are guided. For the modes to be effectively guided in a rib waveguide, the mode effective indices must be greater than the effective index of the slab TE_0 mode [43]. For this reason, an w_1 of 500 nm is chosen. The final width w_2 , on the other hand, has to be chosen to make sure that, at the end of the inverse taper, the modes in the rib waveguide have the best possible overlap with the ideal field excitations of the grating for both polarizations. The ideal excitation fields are defined

Figure 4: Optimization of the antenna footprint. (a,c) P_{upward} as a function of the number of periods in the x (N_x) and y (N_y) directions. (b,d) Beamwidth in the elevation direction θ and the azimuth direction ϕ as a function of N_x and N_y

as the TE_0 and TM_0 mode fields of a $2.9 \mu\text{m}$ wide by 250 nm thick silicon waveguide on an SOI platform with oxide upper cladding. Field overlaps for different rib width w_2 for TE and TM are plotted respectively in Figure 5 (a) and (b). As expected, the best overlap occurs with small rib width. w_2 of 50 nm is chosen as a good compromise between ease of fabrication and device performance. For comparison, the obtained major electric field component for the two polarizations is plot in the inset alongside with the ideal excitation. Finally, the length of the inverse taper L is optimized such that as much as power is coupled into the desired modes while the length is kept as short as possible. Simulations of power coupling at different taper lengths are performed by extracting the corresponding S-parameter using an Eigen Mode Expansion (EME) solver and the results are shown in Figure 5 (c). $L = 11.8 \mu\text{m}$ is selected, which results in estimated power couplings of 92% and 80% for $\text{TE}_0\text{-TE}_0$ and $\text{TM}_0\text{-TM}_0$ transitions respectively.

2.3 3D FDTD simulation results

Before proceeding to fabrication, the overall performance of the antenna (including the injection waveguide) were verified using 3D FDTD simulation centered

Figure 5: Overlap between the rib waveguide mode and the ideal grating excitation field for (a) the TE and (b) the TM fundamental modes. (c) Power coupling between the input and the output of the injection waveguide as a function of the inverse taper length.

Figure 6: (a) Simulated scattering efficiency for both TE and TM polarizations. (b) Farfield radiation pattern for the TE and (c) the TM modes.

at the desired wavelength of $\lambda = 1550$ nm. Simulation results for the upward diffraction efficiency are shown in Figure 6 (a). As can be seen, the antenna achieves a similar scattering efficiency P_{upward} of 53% (-2.8 dB) and 58% (-2.4 dB) for TE and TM modes. Since the grating design was the result of a compromise between TE and TM performance at the wavelength of 1550 nm, the antenna achieves even better TM scattering efficiency above 65% for shorter wavelengths. Moreover, as shown by the far field projection of the scattered field in Figure 6 (b) and (c), the grating scattering occurs at an angle of 10° for both polarizations, confirming the polarization insensitive operation. The beamwidth is also the same for both polarizations, being equal to 9° in the elevation direction θ and 104° in the azimuth direction ϕ . These findings are also summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: Simulated performance of the designed grating antenna

	TE	TM
Diffraction angle	10°	10°
Upward diffraction efficiency	53% (-2.8 dB)	58% (-2.4 dB)
Beamwidth ($\theta \times \phi$)	9°x104°	9.5°x104°

Figure 7: Scanning electron microscopy top view picture of the fabricated grating antenna.

3 Grating coupler antenna fabrication and experimental results

In order to experimentally test the performance of our design, the grating antenna was fabricated on a SOI wafer with a silicon layer thickness of 500 nm and a buried oxide layer thickness of 3 μm . The fabrication process was completed in two steps. Firstly, the SWG metamaterial was created by electron beam lithography, followed by induced coupled plasma (ICP), resulting in a 500 nm etch depth. Next, the partial etched regions in the grating and the rib waveguide were formed using electron beam lithography and ICP etching, achieving a 250 nm etch depth. Finally, we deposited PMMA as the cladding because it has a refractive index similar to that of SiO_2 ($n_{PMMA}=1.49$). A scanning electron microscopy (SEM) image of the fabricated antenna is shown in Figure 7. Two antennas were placed in a back-to-back configuration, connected by a rib waveguide with a length of 5 mm. To facilitate the optical characterization, the scattering efficiency of the antenna was measured using two standard single mode fibers instead of performing direct measurements in free space. The characterization setup is schematically shown in Figure 8. It includes a tunable laser and a polarization controller to set the polarization of the light injected in the grating by the first fiber. 90% of the light collected by the output fiber is sent to the detector while the remaining 10% is fed into a polarimeter. Both input and output fibers have a 10° angle to match the designed emission angle of the antenna. First, light polarization is set to TE using a reference grating with a polarization-dependent transmission realized on the same chip. We then characterize the designed antenna, obtaining the transmission spectrum shown in Figure 9 (a) with a solid blue line. The transmission is normalized to account for both setup losses and the propagation losses of the interconnecting waveguides,

Figure 8: Schematic representation of the experimental setup

which are estimated as 2 dB/cm using an optical frequency domain reflectometry [44]. A peak fiber coupling efficiency of -9 dB is achieved at a wavelength of 1560 nm. We then change the setup polarization to TM using the polarimeter as a reference and measure the normalized transmission spectra shown in Figure 9 (a) with a solid orange line. The same normalization used for TE is applied to TM transmission. In this case, a fiber coupling efficiency of -11.5 dB is obtained at 1560 nm. Figure 9 (b) shows the difference in the fiber coupling efficiency between the TE and TM modes. A perfect polarization-independent operation is achieved at a wavelength of 1532 nm, with a corresponding fiber transmission of -11.5 dB for both TE and TM at this wavelength and a 1-dB polarization insensitive bandwidth of 31 nm.

It should be noted that these results depend on both the upward diffraction efficiency P_{upward} of the antenna and also on the overlap integral of the scattered field with the fiber mode, which was not considered for the design of an antenna for free-space applications. In order to better evaluate the experimental results, we hence simulate the antenna coupling efficiency with a standard single mode fiber with 3D FDTD for both polarizations. Results are reported in Figure 9 (a) with dashed lines and are in a very good agreement with the experiment. The difference between the experimental fiber transmission and the simulation prediction is smaller than 1 dB for both polarizations in the bandwidth of interest, likely due to fabrication tolerances. In the simulations, a perfect polarization insensitive coupling is obtained at a wavelength of 1538 nm, with coupling efficiency of -10.5 dB. Conservatively assuming that the additional 1 dB loss can be entirely attributed to the scattering efficiency and not to the modes overlap, allows to estimate a P_{upward} of about -4 dB (40%) for the fabricated antenna for both TE and TM modes.

4 Conclusion

We designed and fabricated an insensitive polarization grating antenna in a 500 nm SOI platform. The use of SWG metamaterials was key to obtain the same refractive index for TE and TM grating modes and hence the same scattering angle, while the incorporation of the L-shaped section enhanced the diffraction efficiency. In our experimental demonstration, we successfully achieved a 1-dB polarization insensitive bandwidth of 31 nm with an estimated scattering efficiency of about -4 dB (40%). Our design offers a robust solution for efficiently coupling light into photonic integrated circuits regardless of the polarization

Figure 9: Experimental performance of the grating antenna. (a) Measured (solid lines) and simulated (dashed lines) fiber coupling efficiency for both TE and TM polarizations as a function of the wavelength. (b) Difference in TE-TM measured fiber coupling efficiency.

state. By enabling broadband operation, the antenna holds the potential to realize next-generation photonic applications in telecommunications, data centers, and beyond.

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